

Socio-economic Profile of Executives: A Study on Small Industries in Pabna and Bogra Districts

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Abstract: *This paper is based on a survey of the executives belonging to small-scale industries in Pabna and Bogra districts. The main objective of the study is to identify the socio-economic factors that influence the growth and development of small industries. It is found in the study that majority of the executives are relatively middle age and young. Majority of these are with agriculture and business family background. The female employees are very few in the study areas. The largest number of executive had educated themselves up to the level of SSC. In fact, highly educated and technically qualified persons have not yet been attracted to managerial pursuits. The organizational structure is mostly characterized by low specialization and direct supervision by owners. Recruitment is mostly done by personal contact and on-the-job training, if needed.*

Key words: *Small-scale industry, Managerial efficiency, Human resources*

1. Introduction

Small-scale industry plays a vital role in all economics whether developed, developing or underdeveloped. But it occupies a very prominent position in developing and underdeveloped countries of the world. It provides ample scope for achieving the advantage of modern technology and at the same time preserving of traditional technology in a judicious manner. They employ about 5 million people directly and indirectly which account for 82 percent of the total industrial labor force³. They can be set and made to run with little capital and can save foreign currency. They can also preserve heredity, arts and skills and raise local purchasing power. Besides small-scale industries is easy to develop and it does not require highly skilled labors as well as highly developed infrastructural facilities. There is a vast market for small and cottage industries goods because these are usually cheaper. In the international market the demand for SCI goods is also increasing over the year (Jahangir, 1990). So, small-scale industry, the second largest area for employment, remains the only hope for the employment of millions of people in Bangladesh.

The purpose of human resource management is to improve the productive contribution of the people to the organization in ways that are strategically, ethically, and socially responsible (William, 2004). Efficient management of human resources is very important for the survival and development of small industries. The success or failure of the small industries depends upon how the human resources are managed by the small-scale

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³ Planning Commission, *The Fifth Five Year Plan, 1997-02*, GOB, p.325.

entrepreneur. In fact, the human resource management had been given the lesser attention. Therefore, any research conducted to improve the working of the small-scale industries, are of much importance. The present study tried to look into the different aspects to personnel in small industries.

2. Review of the Literature

The paper on "A Study of the Growth of Industrial Entrepreneurship in Bangladesh" approached by M. Akhtaruddin and others (Akhtaruddin & Khatun, 2001), aimed at examining the growth of entrepreneurial endeavour in Bangladesh and motivating the entrepreneurs to choose entrepreneurship careers. The study was based on primary data collected from 70 industrial entrepreneurs whose units were located in the northern districts of Bangladesh. The study revealed that financial assistance from the financial institutions emerged as the chief motivating factor that prompted the entrepreneurs to enter into industry. Other motivational factors in order of preference were, willing to work independently, gaining social prestige, making money and socio-economic development.

Jahangir Hossain Sarder (Jahangir, 1990) had a study on "Potentiality of Small Scale Industries in Bangladesh". He saw that small scale industries played a very important role in the economic development of Bangladesh. The small scale industrial units' accounts for more than 90 percent of the total industrial units, provide nearly 80 percent of the total industrial employment and around 40 percent of the total value added generated in the industrial sector. There are some special characteristics of small industry which claim many advantages over their large counterpart. They can be set and run with small capital, average skill, and available materials and with cheaper labor forces. This paper reveals the development potentiality of this sector so that it can be relied upon as a major source for creating productive employment and income earning opportunity for the years to come.

The major limitation of the above research studies shows that several studies have been conducted in different areas of small industries and most of the studies are general in nature and limited in scope. But no detailed study has been done on human resource management of the small industries in Bangladesh as well as Pabna and Bogra districts. The present study would be pioneering in nature and different from other works relating to objectives, hypotheses, methodological views and procedures to be followed.

3. Significance of the Study

Pabna is said to be the oldest home of the small and cottage industries in Bangladesh. This district is contributing a lot to the small and cottage industrial sector of the country. There are a large number of enterprises of textile industry which create significant impact on the economy of the district by producing employment to the majority of industrial labor force of the district. This district has acquired countrywide reputation for the excellent production of cotton cloths and texture. The position of Bogra in the field of industry is significant amongst the districts of North Bengal and is fast coming up as an industrial zone. At present the small industries in Bogra are engaged in light engineering, textile, carpentry tools, aluminum utensils, pharmaceuticals, steel furniture, food processing etc. However, many units in Pabna and Bogra districts were not able to

function due to a number of reasons. The study would be helpful for small entrepreneurs, BSCIC executives, researchers as well as decision makers that are striving hard for the advancement of SCI sector in Bangladesh.

4. Definition of Small-Scale Industry (SSI)

The term 'Small-Scale Industry' is variously defined in several South Asian countries as well as in the world. In fact the definition has undergone changes over time in most countries. Even within the same country its definition changes periodically. The definition of SSI usually depends on the socio-economic conditions of the country and the policies adopted. The definition of SSI has undergone changes with the increasing pace of inflation, stage of economic development, improvement in technology and the priorities accorded to the development of such industries in the country (Inbalakshmi, 2001).

Small enterprise has been statutory defined in many countries by various institutions and acts connected with small industry development. From the definition employed, in general, it is seen that two criteria are generally used in defining a small enterprise. They are: (a) Criterion of investment, (b) Criterion of employment (Sharma, et. al., 1997).

Besides this, some countries have employed the use of machine power as a subsidiary criterion in defining a small-scale industry.

It has already been mentioned that it is difficult to define the small-scale industry in a precise way as it has been defined in different ways by different persons in different countries. In Bangladesh, small-scale industry has been defined on the basis of capital invested in fixed assets, size of employment, etc. For the purpose of this study the small-scale industry will mean those units whose capital investment in fixed assets excluding land and building did not exceed Tk. 100 million and employing fewer than 100 persons (Ministry of Industries-GOB, 2010).

5. Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are:

To study the socio-economic factors of the executives and the sources of the executives in Pabna and Bogra districts.

To study the salary structure of the executives in the study areas.

To compare the relationship, if any, between age of the executives, working year of the executives, hours of work and salary of the executives of Pabna and Bogra districts.

To provide suggestions for the small entrepreneurs as well as executives to develop their managerial efficiency.

6. Methodology

The Study is based on primary data collected from 222 executives whose units are located in the districts of Pabna and Bogra. There are no published statistics about the total number of executives and workers of small industries in Bangladesh as well as in the study areas. Thus, it is very difficult to select a reliable and representative population and a sample of small enterprises and executives. The researchers interviewed 222

executives of the selected areas. The executives were selected on the basis of the availability of information and their cooperation. So, purposive sampling was done. The data were collected through face-to-face interview with the executives and with the help of a structured questionnaire. Finally, a total of 222 executives in major sectors were interviewed.

7. Sample Design

The major categories of industries covered under the study have been classified into 7 sectors on the basis of nature of products. A picture of the sample size of different sectors is given in Table-1.

Table-1: Sample Size of Different Industries

Sl. No.	Sectors/ Nature of Industry	Total No. of Units		Sample Size		Total Executive
		Pabna	Bogra	Pabna	Bogra	
				Executive	Executive	
1.	Food & Allied	891	1130	42	51	93
2.	Textile, Wearing & Leather	634	63	33	05	38
3.	Engineering	195	537	12	28	40
4.	Printing & Packaging	70	95	08	08	16
5.	Wood & Allied	58	118	05	08	13
6.	Chemical, Plastic & Rubber	23	120	05	07	12
7.	Glass & Ceramic	12	63	05	05	10
Total		1883	2126	110	112	222

Source: Field Study

8. Profile of the Executives

The profile of the executives covering age, parental occupation, education, duration of service, pay levels training, hours of work, etc.

8.1 Age of the Executives

The age-wise classification of the executives of the sample units is presented in Table-2.

Table-2: Age Distribution of Executives

Age (in years)	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Below 30	17	15.6	13	11.6	30	13.5
30-35	25	22.7	8	7.1	33	14.9
35-40	49	44.5	35	31.3	84	37.8
40-45	16	14.5	35	31.3	51	23.0
45-50	1	0.9	3	2.7	4	1.8
50 +	2	1.8	18	16.0	20	9.0
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source: Field study

Table-2 shows that in Pabna district, 1.8 percent executives belong to the age group of 50 & above and in Bogra district, 16 percent executives are involved in the services at the

same range of age. It was further seen that the executive with age of less than 25 years was nil. Moreover, there was no executive with the age exceeding 60 years.

8.2 Parental Occupation of the Executives

The executives seem to have five different family backgrounds namely, farmer, private service, govt. service, business and others. This has been shown in Table-3 below.

Table-3: Parental Occupation of the Executives

Parental Occupation	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Farmer	52	47.3	53	47.3	105	47.3
Private service	18	16.4	22	19.6	40	18.0
Govt. service	2	1.8	1	0.9	3	1.4
Business	27	24.5	25	22.3	52	23.4
Others	11	10.0	11	9.8	22	9.9
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source: Field study

It is seen from the table-3 that 47.3 percent of the executives came from farming background in the maximum cases of Pabna district. The next source was business (24.5%) followed by private service (16.4%), others (10.0%) and govt. service (1.8%) of the district. In Bogra district, maximum executives (47.3%) were with farming as their parental background followed by business (22.3%), private service (19.6%), others (9.8%) and govt. service (0.9%). From the above analysis it may be concluded that the farmer group thus emerged as the dominant source of executives of those districts.

8.3 Educational Status of Executives

The educational qualifications of the executives under the study are presented in Table-4.

Table-4: Educational Qualifications of the Executives

Educational Qualification	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Below SSC	15	13.6	24	21.4	39	17.6
SSC	62	56.4	27	24.1	89	40.0
HSC	14	12.7	49	43.8	63	28.4
Graduate	19	17.3	8	7.1	27	12.2
Post-graduate	00	00	4	3.6	4	1.8
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source: Field study

The aforesaid data indicate that all the two districts are more or less on same footing so far as their low qualified executives are concerned. However, Bogra district is a little better position than that of Pabna district.

8.4 Duration of Service

The duration for which executives have been working in the same unit, has been shown in Table-5.

Table-5: Duration of the Service of the Executives

Duration of Service (years)	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Up to 5	35	31.8	26	23.2	61	27.5
5-10	54	49.1	55	49.1	109	49.1
10-15	16	14.6	25	22.3	41	18.5
15 & above	5	4.5	6	5.4	11	4.9
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source : Field study

The study reveals that out of 222 executives in Pabna and Bogra districts, the majority of the executives (49.1%) have been serving the same unit for a period ranging from 5-10 years while those executives serving the unit for up to 5 years, were 27.5 percent of total executives, 18.5 percent of the executives were ranging between 10-15 years and only 4.9 percent of the executives have served the unit for 15 & above years. The collected data of the Pabna and Bogra districts are shown in separate columns in the table also.

8.5 Pay Levels of the Executives

The general opinion is that small industry pay lower wages to their employees due to their inability to pay higher wages compared to that of the modern and large sector. The average salary of executives in different sample units is shown in Table-6.

Table-6: Distribution of Executives According to Their Salary

Average Salary (per month)	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Below 2000	32	29.1	15	13.4	47	21.2
2000-2500	58	52.7	29	25.9	87	39.2
2500-3000	16	14.5	25	22.3	41	18.4
3000-3500	1	0.9	14	12.5	15	6.8
3500-4000	2	1.8	4	3.6	6	2.7
4000 & above	1	0.9	25	22.3	26	11.7
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source: Field study

Table-6 shows that out of 222 executives of both Pabna and Bogra districts, maximum numbers of executives (39.2%) get the salaries between Tk. 2000 to Tk. 2500 per month while only 2.7 percent executives are given salary in the amount of Tk. 3500 to Tk. 4000 per month. The table also reveals that the executives of 26(11.7%) are given salary in the amount of Tk. 4000 & above. The collected data of the Pabna and Bogra districts are also shown in separate columns in the table.

8.6 Hours of Work

In case the hours of work are long and rest pauses are not adequate, it may become an issue of conflict between the management and employee. Therefore, hours of work should be optimum and proper rest hours should be introduced between each working spell of three or four hours (Dagar, 1993).

Table-7: Distribution of Executives According to Hours of Work per Day

Hours of Work (per day)	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Up to 8	5	4.5	10	8.9	15	6.8
8-10	8	7.3	19	17.0	27	12.1
10-12	31	28.2	34	30.4	65	29.3
12-14	47	42.7	36	32.1	83	37.4
14 & above	19	17.3	13	11.6	32	14.4
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source: Field study

Table-7 reveals that majority of the executives (about 38%) have been working both the districts of Pabna and Bogra for 12-14 hours, the executives of 29.3 percent work for 10-12 hours daily as the second largest time. In Pabna district, out of 110 responding units, the executives of 47(42.7%) units work for 12-14 hours daily in maximum cases. In Bogra district, the responding units are 112 of which the executives of 36(32.1%) units work for 12-14 hours daily in maximum cases. It appears that out of 222 units of Pabna and Bogra districts, the executives of only 15(6.8%) units work for up to 8 hours daily in minimum cases.

To work more than 8 hours is against ILO convention. Recognized working hour is 8 hours with half an hour recess. In case of workers they are entitled to have over-time allowance. But officers are not entitled to that (Rahman, 2004) So they are being deprived in one sense. The above table shows that sometimes they even work up to 16 hours.

8.7 Nature of Training

To develop skill and knowledge, the employees are usually trained in proper way. If the employer fails to provide training, the new employees must proceed by trail and error, frequently with waste of time, materials and money.

Table-8: Nature of Training of the Executives

Particulars	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
On the job	77	70.0	85	75.9	162	73.0
Apprenticeship training	5	4.5	3	2.7	8	3.6
Institutional training	10	9.1	14	12.5	24	10.8
No training	18	16.4	10	8.9	28	12.6
Total	110	100	112	100	222	100

Source: Field study

Table-8 shows that the majority of the executives (73.0%) have got on-the-job training informally in the study areas. It further indicates that 10.8 percent of the executives have got institutional training and only 8 executives have got apprenticeship training, which is only 3.6 percent in both the districts of Pabna and Bogra. The minimum duration of on the job training was 15 days while maximum was 1 year. However, on the job training is unorganized and unsystematic.

8.8 Executive Turnover

The potential executive turnovers in the sample units can be studied with the employees own assessment of their willingness to change the present job. The reasons for willingness as well as unwillingness to change present job were being analyzed.

Table-9: Willingness of Executives to Change the Present Job

Particulars	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Yes	62	63.3	54	52.4	116	57.3
No	36	36.7	49	47.6	85	42.3
Total	98	100	103	100	201	100

Source: Field study

Out of 222 executives, 201 executives are respondents in this context in the districts of Pabna and Bogra jointly. The Table 6.32 indicates that about 63 percent of the executives in Pabna district are willing to change the present job whereas, in Bogra district, 52.4 percent of the executives are willing to change the present job. The reasons for willingness to change the present job are given in Table-10.

Table-10: Reason for Willingness to Change the Present Job

Reason for Change	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Low wages	43	69.4	30	55.5	73	62.9
Irregular earnings	3	4.8	5	9.3	8	6.9
Bad working conditions	2	3.2	4	7.4	6	5.2
Lack of promotion facilities	3	4.8	3	5.6	6	5.2
Lack of job security	5	8.1	4	7.4	9	7.7
Bad relation with owners	2	3.2	1	1.8	3	2.6
Lack of job satisfaction	3	4.8	5	9.3	8	6.9
Other	1	1.6	2	3.7	3	2.6
Total	62	100	54	100	116	100

Source: Field study

The reasons for willingness to change the present job are given in the Table 10. The low wages are considered to be the most important reason for willingness to change the job in the districts of Pabna and Bogra jointly. Of the 201 executives, who are willing to change the job, 73 of them (62.9%) are willing to leave the job because of low wages. 7.7 percent

of the executives are willing to go out of the job because of lack of job security while 6.9 percent are thinking to change the present job because of irregular earnings and lack of job satisfaction. Therefore, the low level of wages and other benefits was the main reason for labor turnover as well as the potential mobility of the employees. Some of the important reasons for unwillingness to change the present job have been given in Table-11.

Table-11: Reason for Unwillingness to Change the Present Job

Reason for Not Change	Pabna		Bogra		Total	
	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%	No. of Executives	%
Good job	3	8.3	4	8.2	7	8.2
Good earnings	2	5.6	5	10.2	7	8.2
Long experience in the present job	7	19.4	12	24.5	19	22.4
No possibility of getting an alternative job	20	55.6	24	49.0	44	51.8
Old age	3	8.3	3	6.1	6	7.1
Other	1	2.8	1	2.0	2	2.3
Total	36	100	49	100	85	100

Source: Field study

The executives who were not willing to change the present job are also asked to give the possible reasons for their unwillingness to change the present job. The Table 6.34 showed that in both the districts of Pabna and Bogra, no possibility of getting an alternative job is the most important reason (about 52%) for the unwillingness to change the present job. Another reason of not leaving the job is the long experience having at the present unit constitutes 22.4 percent. The other reasons of not leaving the present job are good job (8.2%), good earning (8.2%) and old age (7.1%). The collected data of the Pabna and Bogra districts are also shown in separate columns in the table.

8.9: t- Test of Four Selected Variables

The results of the t-test of five selected variables are presented in Table 12.

Table-12: Mean, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of Variation and Results of t-Test and their Significant Level of Selected Characters

Characters	Districts	Range	Mean	SD	CV	t-value	Comments
Age of the executives	Pabna	27-50	36.64	4.98	13.59	4.86	Significant at 1% level
	Bogra	25-52	40.62	7.06	17.38		
Working year of the executives	Pabna	3-23	8.19	4.34	52.99	0.65	Not significant
	Bogra	1-23	8.59	4.8	55.88		
Salary (per month)	Pabna	1800-5000	2402.7	457.86	19.06	5.67	Significant at 1% level
	Bogra	1500-6000	3115.18	1246.85	40.02		
Hours of work (per day)	Pabna	8-16	13.1	2.05	15.65	2.51	Significant at 1% level
	Bogra	8-16	12.37	2.28	18.43		

Source: Field study

Table-12 shows that the age range of the executives in Pabna district is 27-50 years and Bogra district is 25-52 years. The mean and standard deviation of the same character in Pabna district are 36.64 and 4.98 and in Bogra district are 40.62 and 7.06. The 't' value obtained in this case is 4.86, which is highly significant at 0.01 level of confidence. It indicates that the ages of executives in Pabna and Bogra districts differ significantly.

Further, the range of working experience of the executives in Pabna districts is 3.23 years and Bogra districts 1-23 years. The mean and standard deviation of the same character in Pabna district are 8.19 and 4.34 and in Bogra district 8.59 and 4.8 respectively. The 't' value obtained in this case is 0.65 which is not significant at any level of confidence. This shows that the working experience of the executives in Pabna and Bogra districts do not differ significantly. Similarly, the range of working hours in both Pabna and Bogra districts are the same i.e. 8 to 16 hours per day. The mean, standard deviation and CV of the same character in Pabna district are 13.1, 2.05 and 15.65 and in Bogra district are 12.37, 2.28 and 18.43. The 't' value obtained in this case is 2.51, which is highly significant at 0.01 level of confidence. This indicates that the executives of Pabna and Bogra districts differ significantly in regard to working hours.

It may be observed from the table 11 that the small industrial units of the sample pay the salaries between Tk. 1800 to Tk. 5000 per month to the executives in Pabna district and between Tk. 1500 to Tk. 6000 to the executives in Bogra district. The mean and standard deviation values obtained in Pabna district are 2402.7 and 457.86 and in Bogra district are 3115.18 and 1246.85. The 't' value obtained in this case is 5.67, which is highly significant at 0.01 levels. This means that the executives of Bogra district get more salaries than those of Pabna district.

9. Summary of the Findings

Most of the executives (82.8%) at small industrial units in Pabna district fall in the young age group (40 years & below) whereas, management of small industrial units in Bogra district is in the hand of middle (40 - 50 years) and older people (50 & above years). It is seen that the executive with age of less than 25 years is nil. Moreover, there is no executive with age exceeding 52 years of those districts. (Table-2)

The parental background of the executives showed that the highest percentage (47.3%) of executives comes from farming families in both the districts of Pabna and Bogra. The next source was business (23.4%) followed by private service holders (18.0%) and others service (9.9%) holders. The contribution of government service holders (1.4%) is insignificant. The farming group thus emerged as the main source of executives in both districts. (Table-3)

Majority of the executives (57.6%) in study areas are low qualified (SSC & below SSC) and executives with high qualifications are only a few. The two districts are more or less on same footing so far as their low qualified executives are concerned; however, Bogra district is in a slight better state than that of Pabna district.(Table-4)

The salary levels are not same in different small industrial units in Pabna and Bogra districts. The average salaries for different category of executives in Pabna district are Tk. 2402.7 per month and in Bogra district is Tk.3115.18 per month. In fact, the

executives of Bogra district get more salaries than that of Pabna district. However, the salary of the executives of those industries is very low; they do their job for survival because their scope of getting another job is very limited.(Table-6)

Majority of the executives (about 49.0%) have been serving the same unit for a period ranging from 5 to 10 years while those executives serving the unit for up to 5 years, were 27.5 percent of total executives in both Pabna and Bogra districts. Those, who have been serving the unit for 15 & above, were merely 4.9 percent of the total executives. The range of working experience of the executives in Pabna districts is 3-23 years and Bogra district is 1-23 years. The mean duration of the service of the executives in Pabna and Bogra districts was 8.19 and 8.59 respectively. (Tables-5 & 12)

Majority of the executives (about 38%) have been working for 12-14 hours daily in both the districts of Pabna and Bogra even sometimes they work up to 16 hours whereas, the executives of only 15(6.8%) units work for up to 8 hours daily. The mean duration of working hours per day of the executives in Pabna and Bogra districts is 13.1 and 12.37 respectively. To work more than 8 hours is against ILO convention. (Tables 7 & 12)

The low level of wages and other benefits was the main reason for executive turnover as well as the potential mobility of the employees of those districts. (Table 10)

The majority of the executives (73.0%) have got on the job training informally in the study areas. The minimum duration of on the job training was 15 days while maximum was 1 year. However, on the job training is unorganized and unsystematic.(Table-8)

10. Policy Implications

For increasing managerial efficiency the following policy implications are recommended:

Proper attention should be given to the training and development of the executives.

Provision of setting up business training courses for management especially for marketing, business operation, inventory, production, book-keeping and accounting in consultation with small entrepreneurs and executives.

To maintain good employers-employees relations, the small entrepreneurs should observe and follow the provisions of various labor acts and laws.

Labor department of the government can ensure proper wage rate for employees and improve working condition in the small industries by ensuring the concerned industries, full adherence to the labor law of the country.

Government and non-government organizations may adopt appropriate measures for taking care of education and other social services for the children of employees of small industries.

The various personnel policies such as recruitment, selection, promotion and discipline etc., should be drafted and prepared earlier, after due consultations with the employees/unions.

Since majority of the entrepreneurs did not have proper knowledge about the scientific tools, techniques and method of recruitment and selection, therefore, the entrepreneurs should obtain proper knowledge about them, through managerial development program organized by Government, autonomous bodies or professional institutions.

Small industrial units should prepare “organization chart” and be it known to every body. Moreover, job description for every organizational position should be prepared in writing.

Executives should be given sufficient authority to perform their work or to carry on their responsibilities so that an organization could get an uninterrupted work.

Small-scale industries need up-dated technology on a continuous basis. They should be encouraged to use information technology to increase productivity. Effectives software has been developed, which help eliminate waste, increase efficiency and production quality.

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Appendix:

Questionnaire for Executives

(Your answers in this questionnaire would be kept strictly confidential. They are to be used only for research purposes)

1. Name:
2. Name and address of the firm:
3. Designation:
4. Sex: Male Female

Age of the Executive:

- | | |
|--------------------------|------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Below 30 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 30 - 35 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 35 - 40 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 40 - 45 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 45 - 50 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | 50 & Above |

Marital Status:

- Married Unmarried

7. Number of children:
8. Father's name:
9. Father's occupation:
10. Data of joining in this firm:

Do you have any experience before joining this firm?

- Yes No

Educational qualification:

- | | |
|--------------------------|------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Below SSC |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | SSC |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | HSC |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Graduate |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Post-graduate & others |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Others |

13. Salary (per month)

- Below of Tk. 2000
- Tk. 2000-2500
- Tk. 2500-3000
- Tk. 3000-3500
- Tk. 3500-4000
- Tk. 4000-Above

How many hours do you work per day?

- Up to 8 hours
- 8-10 hours
- 10-12 hours
- 12-14 hours
- 14 & above
- No particular time

Do you get overtime facilities?

- Yes No

What are your leave facilities?

- Weekly holiday
- Casual leave
- Maternal leave
- Govt. holiday
- Earn leave
- Medical leave
- Other
- None of the above

Do you have promotion facilities?

- Yes No

How is the labour-management relation in your organization?

- Excellent Good Moderately Bad Very bad

What financial facilities do your get?

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------|--------------------------|--------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Medical facilities | <input type="checkbox"/> | Dividend on profit |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Insurance | <input type="checkbox"/> | Festival bonus |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | House rent | <input type="checkbox"/> | Addition bonus |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Provident fund | <input type="checkbox"/> | Others benefits |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Pension | <input type="checkbox"/> | None of the above |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Gratuity | | |

Participation in training (if any)

- Yes No

If yes please state the type of training

Name of the training	Duration
<input type="checkbox"/> On the job training	
<input type="checkbox"/> Apprenticeship training	
<input type="checkbox"/> Institutional training	

Do you like to change the job?

- Yes No

If yes, what are the causes?

- Low wages
- Irregular earnings
- Bad working conditions
- Lack of promotion facilities
- Lack of job security
- Bad relation with owners
- Lack of job satisfaction
- Others

If not, what are the causes?

- Good job
- Good earning
- Long experience in the present job
- No possibility of getting an alternative job
- Old age
- Others